

ENERGY SECURITY: IRAN AND CENTRAL ASIA COOPERATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929017>

Energy security is a key aspect of international relations, especially for countries with rich natural resources. The Islamic Republic of Iran and Central Asia represent significant regions where energy cooperation can not only enhance economic stability but also improve energy security. This thesis examines the main aspects of energy cooperation between both Iran and Central Asia, as well as the challenges and opportunities that arise in this context.

1) Energy potential of Iran and Central Asian countries. Iran has some of the largest oil and gas reserves in the world, making it a significant player in the global energy arena. In particular, Iran ranks fourth in the world in terms of oil reserves and has 158 billion barrels of proven crude oil reserves. This figure is about 10% of the world's oil reserves. In addition to its significant oil reserves, the country also has the world's second-largest natural gas reserves, estimated at more than 1,200 trillion cubic feet. Iran accounts for almost half of OPEC's proven natural gas reserves.

Central Asia, in turn, is also rich in hydrocarbon resources, especially Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan (specifically, Central Asia has more than 7% of the world's oil reserves, more than 10% of gas reserves, and is home to about 20% of the world's uranium reserves). Cooperation between these regions can lead to the creation of efficient energy corridors that help diversify supplies and reduce dependence on traditional routes. For example, an assessment of oil and gas reserves in the region could confirm the possibility of market integration.

2) Security issues. Energy security is closely linked to political stability. Regional conflicts, such as the confrontation between Iran and the West, can negatively affect energy cooperation. In addition, terrorist groups, the serious geopolitical struggles of the major actors in the region, and their cooperative relations may pose a threat to joint energy projects with Iran. For example, the impact of the political situation in Afghanistan on projects such as TAPI needs to be analyzed.

3) Opportunities for cooperation. Despite the challenges, there are significant opportunities to deepen cooperation. Gas pipeline and power grid projects, such as TAPI, can help integrate markets and ensure energy security. It

is important to discuss the potential benefits of Iran's participation in this project, which will improve access to South Asian markets.

4) Environmental aspects. Cooperation in the field of renewable energy is becoming an important area. Iran and Central Asian countries can jointly develop solar and wind energy projects that will help reduce carbon footprint and improve the environmental situation in the region. Specific initiatives such as joint research programs and technologies that can be applied to improve the environmental situation should be considered. According to experts, Iran actually has the capacity to generate 100,000 MW of electricity from solar energy. Currently, the country has about 90 solar power plants with a capacity of more than 1 MW. According to the information of the Ministry of Energy of Iran, 55 hydroelectric power plants with a capacity of more than 13 thousand megawatts are operating in Iran today.

At this point, it also should be noted that according to the Eurasian Development Bank, the hydropower potential of Central Asia is 930 billion kWh per year. In other words, this indicator is equal to 5.5% of the world share. However, to date, only 11% of the opportunities in this regard are being used.

In conclusion, Energy cooperation between the Islamic Republic of Iran and the countries of Central Asia is a promising area that requires a comprehensive approach to the issues of security, political stability and sustainable development. Deepening ties in this field can contribute to the economic growth of the participating countries and enhance energy security at the regional and global levels. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to overcome existing barriers and develop trusting relations between states. It is recommended to develop specific measures aimed at strengthening cooperation, including joint negotiations, establishment of joint working groups and attracting investment.

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